

IPAlliance – Integrated Platform for Lifelong Learning and Training of Healthcare Professionals: Data Management Plan

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Project abstract

The IP Alliance is a multidisciplinary and interprofessional health education alliance that aims to contribute to improved control of communicable and non-communicable diseases and to address several of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (3 - Better Health, 4 – Quality Education, 5 – Gender Equality, and 9 – Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure). Created as a Portuguese alliance between the Nursing School of Porto, the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto, and the Health School of the Polytechnic Institute of Porto, IP Alliance is supported by the NextGenerationEU fund. This partnership aims to promote re-skilling and up-skilling of healthcare professionals, focusing on the leading global health challenges, and optimize the quality and safety of interventions by health professionals through training in a simulated environment of clinical skills and improving the training of students by promoting learning in simulated scenarios (Padilha et al., 2021). It will also promote the development of three simulation centers transforming the Porto

Innovation District¹ (Pereira, 2020) into a reference in health education in Europe.to become a reference in health education in Europe.

Keywords: Lifelong training; Global health; Health Education; Simulation in Health

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1. Output summary (Data collection)

The IPAlliance project aims to promote the training of health professionals. Throughout the project's development, data will be collected and processed and then organized into RAW data, processed data, and public data. (see details in Tables 1, 2 and 3)

RAW data will have two types of access - closed and open. Closed data includes sensitive, private, confidential, and personal information and cannot be opened to the public. Open data are data made available from the OpenEdX platform managed and created by the Portuguese Agency for Research and Technology - NAU Platform, where the MOOC Courses will be made available (Table 2).

Data will also be collected from data processed by NAU referring to the evaluation of the trainees attending the courses. These data are extracted into Excel files and properly anonymized (Table 3).

¹ An innovation district is a physically compact urban location that concentrates on advanced training activities, science production, technology and innovation-based co-creation of value by different players, alongside companies, hospital institutions, and startups whose proposed value is based on knowledge, within an environment with urban quality, filled with commercial, residential and amenities spaces (Katz & Wagner, 2014; Wagner, Katz & Osha, 2019). The Porto Innovation District is a square mile area, traditionally named Asprela University Pole, located in Porto, Portugal (Pereira, 2020), that comprises more than 16 tertiary institutions, 26 R&D Units and Research Laboratories, 3 Hospital Centers and more than 70 startups to be incubated in a Science and Technology Park. This one square kilometre area serves as a residential area for over 20,000 people and working area for more than 14,000 people, most with higher education studies and specialized expertise. The Innovation District also comprises around 38,000 students distributed into more than 500 higher education courses and prepares more than 10,000 graduates per year for the labour market, corresponding to about a third of the overall graduates of the northern region of Portugal.

1.1 Data created/collected/reused during the operation of the IP Alliance

Type	Instrument for collecting	Data Owner	Storage/ Access rights	License/ Restriction	Expected format and size
Data without any sensitive, personal or private information	Different types of activities and financial reports Data and materials for dissemination events (workshops, social networks, meetings, training courses, and education activities, among others.) Documents related to the Open Call Assessment of the IP Alliance performance	Nursing School of Porto, the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto and the School of Health of the Polytechnic Institute of Porto	OSF (Open Science Framework)	Only for team members that can create new content	.PDF .xls .doc .html
Sensitive data	Collecting personal data for the enrolment in the interprofessional courses to be created and those already integrated into the Alliance.	Nursing School of Porto, the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto and the School of Health of the Polytechnic Institute of Porto FCT – Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology Portuguese Directorate General for Higher Education (DGES) NextGenerationEU Management Agency	Internal servers of the data owners. Access only by project's members and qualified academic, technical, and financial staff of the data owners.	Only for internal data owners and funded agency staff	.PDF .xls .doc
Private	Minutes of the meetings of the Executive Board and the Consultancy Board. Identification data of the number of students enrolled in the courses to be created.	Nursing School of Porto, the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto and the School of Health of the Polytechnic Institute of Porto	OSF (Open Science Framework)	Only for team members	.PDF .doc

Confidential	Informed consent	Nursing School of Porto, the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto and the School of Health of the Polytechnic Institute of Porto	NAU Platform	Only for team members	.html
Another type without any sensitive, personal, or private information. Public	OpenEdX platform – NAU platform	Nursing School of Porto, the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto and the School of Health of the Polytechnic Institute of Porto FCT - Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology	NAU Platform	Creative Commons CC BY-NC-ND 4.0	5 MOOCs
Processed	Videos; Word documents; Pdf documents; Html documents.	Nursing School of Porto, the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto and the School of Health of the Polytechnic Institute of Porto	NAU Platform and institutional LMS of each partner institution.	Creative Commons CC BY-NC-ND 4.0	Overall: 264 documents

Table 1. Information about data created/collected/reused during the operation of the IP Alliance

1.2 MOOC Courses DATA

The five MOOC courses combine the following elements (see Table 2): prerequisite questionnaire; quick lessons; video lectures on various topics; interactive quizzes; course evaluation questionnaire to measure short-term learning outcomes (a complete course outline is available on the NAU platform). Students must complete a prerequisite questionnaire to attend courses.

The development of five lifelong training massive open online courses with a multidisciplinary nature aims to train health professionals to effectively contribute to the prevention and treatment of non-communicable diseases.

Course Introduction	All the MOOC courses
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Hemorrhagic Stroke: Prevention, Treatment and Rehabilitation	<p>14 quick lessons with a handle hyperlink from the institutional repository and with a DOI address;</p> <p>14 videos included in the National educational videos' repository named Educast with a Creative Commons CC BY-NC-ND 4.0;</p> <p>5 interactive quizzes integrated into the OpenEdX NAU Platform;</p> <p>1 Course evaluation questionnaire.</p>
Ischemic Stroke: Prevention, Treatment and Rehabilitation	<p>16 quick lessons with a handle hyperlink from the institutional repository and with a DOI address;</p> <p>16 videos included in the National educational videos' repository named Educast with a Creative Commons CC BY-NC-ND 4.0;</p> <p>5 interactive quizzes integrated into the OpenEdX NAU Platform;</p> <p>1 Course evaluation questionnaire.</p>
COPD prevention and management: a multidisciplinary approach	<p>26 quick lessons with a handle hyperlink from the institutional repository and with a DOI address;</p> <p>23 videos included in the National educational videos' repository named Educast with a Creative Commons CC BY-NC-ND 4.0;</p> <p>5 interactive quizzes integrated into the OpenEdX NAU Platform;</p> <p>1 Course evaluation questionnaire.</p>
Acute Myocardial Infarction prevention and management: a multidisciplinary approach	<p>13 quick lessons with a handle hyperlink from the institutional repository and with a DOI address;</p> <p>13 videos included in the National educational videos' repository named Educast with a Creative Commons CC BY-NC-ND 4.0;</p> <p>5 interactive quizzes integrated into the OpenEdX NAU Platform;</p> <p>1 Course evaluation questionnaire.</p>
Heart Failure: Prevention and management	<p>9 quick lessons with a handle hyperlink from the institutional repository and with a DOI address;</p> <p>9 videos included in the National educational videos' repository named Educast with a Creative Commons CC BY-NC-ND 4.0;</p> <p>5 interactive quizzes integrated into the OpenEdX NAU Platform;</p> <p>1 Course evaluation questionnaire.</p>

Table 2 – ESEP 5 MOOC Curriculum Outline

1.3 Processed data extracted from the NAU platform

For the final evaluation, a questionnaire composed of two sections was applied. The first section includes a brief sociodemographic characterization, and the second section is composed of 3 surveys: Quest 1 - Overall course evaluation (12 questions); Quest 2 - Usability evaluation (10 questions); and Quest 3 - Self-efficacy perception evaluation (10 questions). For Quest 1 and 2, responses were rated on a five-point Likert scale (1 - worst possible opinion, 5 - best possible opinion), and for Quest 3, a four-point scale was used (1 - Extremely false, 4 - Extremely true).

The assessment of the effectiveness of the training in the acquisition and consolidation of skills and knowledge by health professionals will be evaluated through a comparative analysis of the

results obtained, by each trainee, in the diagnostic test against the assessment and results obtained in the modular evaluation of the parts of the course. These diagnostic assessments are composed of three questions for each module of each course that will integrate the set of questions for the final assessment of each module to identify patterns of improvement in the effectiveness of the course for the acquisition and consolidation of clinical skills. The dataset that results from this data collection will be called Processed Data (see Table 3) and will be converted into an Excel table without sensitive and/or confidential data.

Type	Instrument for data collection
Questionnaire divided into two sections	The first section included a brief sociodemographic characterization
	The second section was composed of 3 surveys: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Quest 1 - Global assessment of the course (12 questions); ● Quest 2 - Usability assessment (10 questions); ● Quest 3 - Assessment of self-efficacy perception (10 questions). For Quest 1 and 2, answers were rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1-worst possible opinion, 5-best possible opinion). For Quest 3, a 4-point scale was used (1-Extremely Untrue, 4-Extremely True).
Diagnostic evaluation	Three questions for each module of each course that will integrate the set of questions for the final evaluation of each module to identify patterns of improvement in the effectiveness of the course for the acquisition and consolidation of clinical skills.

Table 3 – Processed data collected from the NAU platform

In addition to the datasets presented in Tables 1, 2 and 3, the following publications are planned:

- Activity and financial reports;
- Data and materials from outreach events (workshops, social media posts, meetings, training courses, educational activities, among others);
- Open Call related documents;
- Opinion of the Ethics Committee
- Informed consent will be made available on the OpenEdX platform for participants during the registration process for each course, based on the Personal Data Protection Policy of each partner institution;
- Evaluation of the performance of the IP Alliance Project.

Documents will be published on the OSF page of the IPAlliance project with a private profile. The public results will be published online at <http://i-d.esenf.pt/ipalliance/> and in dissemination events such as invited lectures and free presentations, among others.

During some training courses or education activities, personal and sensitive data can be collected (country, gender, among others). Data will be treated accordingly to the General Data Protection Regulation.

The collected data which includes sensitive and personal information, will not be publicly available but will be reported in the mandatory periodic reports mandated by the funding agency after the processing and anonymization, used for internal studies and analysis to verify the execution of the project. The collected data to be published in Open Access will be anonymized.

Before collecting sensitive and personal data, all participants will be provided with detailed information about the purpose of the project, the objective of the data collection, and authorization of using these data for analysis purposes and asked to sign informed consent.

Information about data is displayed in Tables 1, 2, and 3, which will be updated during the execution of the IP Alliance.

2. Responsibilities

2.1 Promotor: Nursing School of Porto

2.2 Partners: Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto and the School of Health of the Polytechnic Institute of Porto

2.3 Executive board: Director - Miguel Padilha. Executive board members - Virgínia Moreira, Abel Nicolau, Nuno Rocha

2.4 Responsible for the collection/creation of data: Abel Nicolau, Carla Fernandes, Cláudia Moreira, Clemente Sousa, Cristina Alves, Francisco Vieira, Miguel Padilha, Nuno Rocha, Olga Ribeiro, Paula Fonseca, Paula Teixeira, Sérgio Malta, Virgínia Moreira

2.5 Responsible for DMP-related processes: Mafalda Lopes (lauralopes@senf.pt), Francisco Vieira (franciscovieira@senf.pt), Miguel Padilha (miguelpadilha@esenf.pt), Yulia Karimova (ylaleo@gmail.com)

All partners and members of the IP Alliance will follow the created DMP. The DMP will be monitored and updated according to the IP Alliance development. Also, the DMP will follow the recommendations of Horizon Europe, which in turn follows GDPR and RDM requirements such as open-science and FAIR principles. The DMP will be seen as the output of the IP Alliance activities and published on Zenodo with DOI assignment.

3. FAIR data

3.1 Findability

To ensure that the data is findable, the processed data will be used for scientific publications and made available in open access from the community created for the project on Zenodo. This allows the DOI assignment to make datasets more findable, accessible, and reusable by others.

The data collected/created during the training programmes' operation will not be publicly available. All data will be used for internal activities, processes, and needs.

More information about data is detailed in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

3.2 Accessibility

Data with any sensitive and personal information will be accessible only to the project's members and stored on internal servers of the Nursing School of Porto (data for students enrolled in 6 Masters, 33 micro-credentials and 5 MOOCs) of the School of Health of the Polytechnic Institute of Porto (data for students enrolled in 2 CTESP courses and 1 post-graduation course), of the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto (data for students enrolled in 5 short courses) and FCT - Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (data for students enrolled in 5 MOOCs).

Sensitive and personal data will be accessible only for internal use and destroyed as soon as possible after processing.

3.3 Interoperability

To ensure the interoperability of the data, the preferred file formats will be *.xls/.xlsx, *.doc/.docx, *.pdf, *.mp4.

3.4 Reusability

Data without sensitive and personal information can be reusable by members of the project in similar studies with a Share-Alike license, allowing the sharing of data CC BY-NC-ND 4.0 (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/>);

Share, copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format. Under the following terms:

- Attribution — It needs appropriate credit, a link to the license, and indication of performed changes. You may do so in any reasonable manner but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.
- NonCommercial — You may not use the material for commercial purposes.
- NoDerivatives — If you remix, transform, or build upon the material, you may not distribute the modified material.
- No additional restrictions — You may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits.

4. Data security

The data collected during the development of the project will be kept and preserved for as long as necessary.

- a) Data retrieval processing, secure storage, and transfer of sensitive data will comply with the ESEP procedures in the academic management of student files. These procedures will be detailed in the next version of this DMP;
- b) Data without any sensitive and personal information will be preserved on the internal servers of the Nursing School of Porto (data for students enrolled in 6 Masters, 33 micro-credentials and 5 MOOCs) of the School of Health of the Polytechnic Institute of Porto (data for students enrolled in 2 CTESP courses and 1 post-graduation course), of the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto (data for students enrolled in 5 short courses) and FCT - Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (data for students enrolled in 5 MOOCs) for 5-10 years for internal use;
- c) Sensitive and personal data will be destroyed as soon as possible after processing.

5. Other matters

The DMP will be monitored at least every six months. Monitoring will focus on registering the needed changes of the project related to RDM and in all aspects related to the research data management issues. Moreover, it can also clarify the aspects concerning the publication of the datasets (if deemed necessary) and their detailed description.

The IP Alliance website (<http://i-d.esenf.pt/ipalliance>) will be one of the tools to disseminate and communicate results to common citizens and the overall community.

This DMP will be published on Zenodo with DOI assignment and will be citable.

IPR ownership of data produced during the project is from the project team.

6. Complementary information

If more sensitive, private, or personal data becomes available during the operation of the IP Alliance and requires publication, the collaboration of the Data Protection Officer can be considered. More information on this aspect will be added later in future versions of the DMP.

The expected amount of data to be stored will be determined later and added to Table 1.

The project foresees the creation of:

- 1 Center for Health Education
- 3 Simulation Centers
- 52 interprofessional courses, namely 5 MOOCs, 6 Master's degrees, 33 Microcredentials, 5 short courses, 2 CTESP courses, 1 Post-graduation course.

7. References

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